

SOME ALIPHATIC MONOCARBOXYLATE COMPLEXES OF BIVALENT METALS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART I. LEAD MONO-ACETATO COMPLEX

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The composition of the complex formed between Pb^{2+} and acetate ions has been found to be $PbAc^+$ from a study of the equilibrium H^+ -ion concentrations in mixtures of equimolecular lead nitrate and acetic acid solutions by "Job's method of continued variation" using a new index property, viz., the increase of H^+ -ion concentration.

The thermodynamic dissociation constant, K , for the equilibrium, $PbAc^+ \rightleftharpoons Pb^{2+} + Ac^-$, has been found out as 3.31×10^{-3} at $32.0^\circ - 30.0^\circ$ by the direct application of "law of mass action", taking into account the activity coefficients of the individual ions, calculated from the ionic strength of the solution mixtures of lead nitrate and acetic acid, employing the "Debye-Hückel limiting law".

Job's method of continued variation (*Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928; *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113) has been extensively used in determining the composition of a compound A_mB_n formed in aqueous solution between two molecular or ionic entities, 'A' and 'B'. The method, to a less extent, has been applied to find out the dissociation constant of such a compound. In this method, the difference 'Y' between the value of an additive molecular property (e.g. molar extinction, molar conductivity etc.) calculated for any mixture of 'x' c.c. of a solution of 'B' of molar concentration 'pC' and '1-x' c.c. of a solution of 'A' of molar concentration 'C', and the observed value of the property for the mixture is determined. The plot of 'Y' against 'x' here gives a curve with a maximum or a minimum. From the value of 'x' at the maximum or the minimum point, the ratio m/n (i. e. composition of the complex) and the dissociation constant 'K' of the complex,

$$\left(K = \frac{A^m B^n}{A_m B_n} \right),$$

are determined using equimolecular ($p=1$) and non-equimolecular ($p \neq 1$) parent solution respectively.

The method has been described in detail by Siddhanta (this *Journal*, 1948, 26, 579) and by Martell and Calvin ("Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds" Prentice-Hall, Inc., New York, 1952).

Various such additive molar properties were used for this purpose by different workers in the past; e. g., molar extinction coefficient used first by Job (*loc. cit.*) and afterwards by a good number of other workers (vide Martell and Calvin, *loc. cit.*, pp. 29, 34); molar refractivity used by Spacu and Popper (*Bull. Soc. Stiinta, Cluj*, 1934, 7, 400; 1934, 8, 5); molar conductivity used first by Purkayastha and Sen Sarma (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 31) and subsequently by others; molar heat content by Siddhanta (*loc. cit.*).

In the present work it has been observed that, on mixing lead nitrate and acetic acid solutions, there is a considerable fall in p_H , indicating the liberation of hydrogen ions through a reaction like,

a complete dissociation for the acid, $\text{H}_n(\text{Pb}_m \text{Ac}_n)$ being assumed. There are many such reactions involving complex formation in solution in which the acidity of the medium increases.

In any such case, suppose $[\text{H}^+]_A$ is the H^+ -ion concentration of $(1-x)$ volume of a solution of 'A' diluted to a volume 1, and $[\text{H}^+]_B$ is that of ' x ' volume of a solution of 'B' diluted to a volume 1. Now, if $[\text{H}^+]_{\text{obs}}$ is the hydrogen-ion concentration of the mixture of $(1-x)$ volume of 'A' and ' x ' volume of 'B', then the increase in H^+ -ion concentration due to complex formation is given by

$$Y = [\text{H}^+]_{\text{obs}} - \{ [\text{H}^+]_A + [\text{H}^+]_B \}.$$

For the purpose of evaluating 'Y', however, no distinction has been made between ' a_{H^+} ' and $[\text{H}^+]$, i. e. ' a_{H^+} ', as calculated from the observed p_H of the solution, has been taken equal to $[\text{H}^+]$ for every solution.

If the reactant 'A' is a neutral substance like Pb^{2+} ion, and the reactant 'B' be a weak acid like HAc , it is easy to see that the value of 'Y' for any mixture is approximately, though not strictly, proportional to the concentration of the complex $\text{A}_m \text{B}_n$. Therefore a plot of 'Y' against ' x ' would show a maximum, where $[\text{A}_m \text{B}_n]$ is maximum. Hence, we propose for such cases that the increase in acidity 'Y' may be used for applying Job's method for the determination of the composition of the complex, using equimolecular parent solutions.

Following such a procedure and employing equimolecular parent solutions of lead nitrate and acetic acid, it has been found in the present work that all the three sets of independent $Y-x$ plots, obtained (Fig. 1), show a maximum value of 'Y' for $x = 0.5$. At this point,

$$m/n = (1-x)/x = 1$$

and the reacting proportion of lead nitrate and acetic acid is 1:1. Assuming that lead nitrate and nitric acid undergo complete dissociation, the reaction can therefore be written as

The complete dissociation of lead nitrate in dilute aqueous solution has already been established by Prasad and Aditya (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 683). The maxima in all the three curves are clear and unequivocal, showing that no higher complexes, e.g. PbAc_2 , $[\text{PbAc}_2]^-$, are formed to any appreciable extent under the conditions of the experiment.

In the present work, Job's method for determining the dissociation constant 'K' for the complex PbAc^+ has not been used since (i) the curve in Job's method as a rule does not show a sharp maximum; consequently it involves the error in locating the maximum point; (ii) the method is indirect as the maximum point of the curve is to be obtained by interpolation; and (iii) the proportionality of 'Y' and $[\text{PbAc}^+]$ is not rigorously true,

A direct method for determining the thermodynamic dissociation constant of PbAc^+ ion, described below, has been used in the present work in preference to Job's method.

In any mixture of lead nitrate and acetic acid in aqueous solution, the existence of the following equilibria are feasible in addition to the one represented by eq. (A).

The existence of lead diacetate or lead polyacetate ions or polymeric lead acetate complexes is improbable for reasons stated afterwards (vide Discussion), and therefore they need not be considered.

Using symbols with usual meanings, the dissociation constant of PbAc^+ ion (eq. B) is given by

$$K = \frac{a_{\text{Pb}^{2+}} \cdot a_{\text{Ac}^-}}{a_{\text{PbAc}^+}} = \frac{c_{\text{Pb}^{2+}} \cdot c_{\text{Ac}^-}}{c_{\text{PbAc}^+}} + \frac{f_{\text{Pb}^{2+}} \cdot f_{\text{Ac}^-}}{f_{\text{PbAc}^+}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The total acetate entity taken is given by

$$C_a = C_x = c_{\text{PbAc}^+} + c_{\text{Ac}^-} + c_{\text{HAc}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The undissociated acetic acid remaining at equilibrium is given by

$$c_{\text{HAc}} = C_a - c_{\text{H}^+} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Since part of the acetic acid originally added reacts according to (A) and another part dissociates according to (C), and the rest remains undissociated.

If ' K_a ' is the ionisation constant of acetic acid (eq. C), we have,

$$c_{\text{Ac}^-} = \frac{K_a \cdot c_{\text{HAc}}}{c_{\text{H}^+} \cdot f_{\text{H}^+} \cdot f_{\text{Ac}^-}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

assuming $f_{\text{HAc}} = 1$, HAc being a non-electrolyte. Combining equations (2) and (3), we have

$$c_{\text{PbAc}^+} = c_{\text{H}^+} - c_{\text{Ac}^-} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

Again, $c_{\text{Pb}^{2+}}$ = total Pb^{2+} ions originally taken - lead in the complex

$$= C(1-x) - c_{\text{PbAc}^+} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

assuming complete dissociation for lead nitrate.

To evaluate the activity coefficients, we need know the ionic strength, ' μ ', of the solution given by the expression,

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2} (4c_{\text{Pb}^{2+}} + c_{\text{PbAc}^+} + c_{\text{H}^+} + c_{\text{NO}_3^-} + c_{\text{Ac}^-}) \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

Then, the activity coefficients can be calculated by applying the "Debye-Hückel limiting law" as shown below:

$$f_{\text{H}^+} = f_{\text{Ac}^-} = f_{\text{PbAc}^+} = f_1 = \text{antilog} \{ -0.51\sqrt{\mu} \} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (8a)$$

$$\text{and, } f_{\text{Pb}^{2+}} = f_2 = f_1^4 = \text{antilog} \{ -4 \times 0.51\sqrt{\mu} \} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (8b)$$

taking 0.51 to be the Debye-Hückel constant at the temperature of the experiment. For the first approximation, we assume the applicability of the "Debye-Hückel limiting law" to the dilutions used.

From our experimental procedure of determining the $\phi_{\pm}$ of solution mixtures of lead nitrate and acetic acid after attainment of equilibrium, we can know the value of ' a_{H^+} ' at equilibrium. For the purpose of evaluation of ' f_1 ' and ' f_2 ',* we take " $a_{\text{H}^+} = c_{\text{H}^+}$ " and find ' c_{HAc} ' from equation (3); this does not involve a serious error since " $C_{\text{H}^+} \gg c_{\text{H}^+} > c_{\text{H}^+} - a_{\text{H}^+}$ ". Then, we may find out the value of ' a_{Ac^-} ' for knowing ' a_{PbAc^+} ' from a modification of equation (5), viz.

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 c_{\text{PbAc}^+} &= f_1 c_{\text{H}^+} - f_1 c_{\text{Ac}^-} \\ \text{OR } a_{\text{PbAc}^+} &= a_{\text{H}^+} - a_{\text{Ac}^-} \end{aligned} \quad \dots (5a)$$

We then, approximately evaluate ' $c_{\text{Pb}^{2+}}$ ' by putting " $c_{\text{PbAc}^+} = a_{\text{PbAc}^+}$ " in equation (6); this also does not cause a serious error since, " $C_{\text{I-x}} \gg c_{\text{PbAc}^+} > c_{\text{PbAc}^+} - a_{\text{PbAc}^+}$ ".

Now, we evaluate ' μ ' from equation (7) by putting " $c_{\text{Ac}^-} = a_{\text{Ac}^-}$ ", " $c_{\text{PbAc}^+} = a_{\text{PbAc}^+}$ " and " $a_{\text{H}^+} = c_{\text{H}^+}$ ", and this also does not cause a large error since,

$$"(4c_{\text{Pb}^{2+}} + c_{\text{NO}_3^-}) \gg (c_{\text{PbAc}^+} + c_{\text{H}^+} + c_{\text{Ac}^-}) > [(c_{\text{PbAc}^+} + c_{\text{H}^+} + c_{\text{Ac}^-}) - (a_{\text{PbAc}^+} + a_{\text{H}^+} + a_{\text{Ac}^-})]"$$

' $c_{\text{NO}_3^-}$ ' is taken equal to ' $2C_{\text{I-x}}$ ', assuming complete dissociation for lead nitrate.

From this value of ' μ ', which is fairly accurate, ' f_1 ' and ' f_2 ', are calculated by applying equations (8a) and (8b).

Now, we can put " $c_{\text{H}^+} = \frac{a_{\text{H}^+}}{f_1}$ ", and recalculate a more accurate value of ' c_{HAc} ' and

hence of ' c_{Ac^-} ' from equations (3) and (4) respectively. Using this new value of ' c_{Ac^-} ' a more accurate value of ' c_{PbAc^+} ' and ' $c_{\text{Pb}^{2+}}$ ' can be calculated from equations (5) and (6) respectively. Putting the corrected values, thus obtained, in equation (1) in a slightly modified form, viz.,

$$K = \frac{c_{\text{Pb}^{2+}} \cdot c_{\text{Ac}^-}}{c_{\text{PbAc}^+}} \cdot f_2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots (1a)$$

we can calculate the value of ' K '.

* The terms 'activity' and 'activity coefficient' can have a physical significance only in the case of a thermodynamic component. An individual ion cannot be regarded as thermodynamic component, *i. e.* an independently variable constituent, since the amounts of positive and negative ions are interdependent. Hence, the use of ' f_1 ' and ' f_2 ' etc. as activity coefficients of individual ion for the purpose of evaluating thermodynamic constant ' K ', is theoretically objectionable. We may point out that no theoretical objection can arise, if we regard ' f_1 ' and ' f_2 ' as multiplication operators rather than definite thermodynamic quantities.

The values of ' K ', calculated by such a method in different solution mixtures, are not, however, accurate since they are dependent on the ionic strength of the respective solutions; for though the values of ionic strengths ' μ ' are fairly accurate, the values of the activity coefficients ' f_1 ' and ' f_2 ', calculated from the 'Debye-Hückel limiting law' are somewhat approximate, the law being inapplicable to solutions with finite ionic strengths. The error in ' K ', calculated as above, is therefore greater and greater in cases of solutions with larger and larger ionic strengths; hence, there is a progressive increase in the values of ' K ' in Table II with increasing dilution.

The dependence of ' K ', so calculated, on the respective ionic strengths of the corresponding solution mixtures is proved clearly by plotting ' K ' against ' μ ', which process yields one smooth single curve, using data from Table II (vide Fig. 2). This curve, when extrapolated to zero ionic strength, should give the true value of the thermodynamic constant ' K ' (when $f_1 = f_2 = 1$). But such an extrapolation may be regarded as objectionable, since the slope of the curve in different regions of the extrapolated portion is unknown. We have, however, found that when $pK (= -\log K)$ is plotted against $\sqrt{\mu}^*$, it gives a straight line curve, which satisfies all the experimental data obtained (vide Fig. 3). The extrapolation of this straight line to $\sqrt{\mu} = 0$ is less objectionable, and in this way therefore we can find a very accurate value of ' K '.

EXPERIMENTAL

Exact 0.1 M , 0.2 M and 0.333 M solutions of lead nitrate (E. Merck, Darmstadt) were prepared by direct weighing of the calculated amounts. Acetic acid (Analar) solutions of strengths 0.1 M , 0.2 M and 0.333 M were prepared (standardised against standard caustic soda solution). All solutions and dilutions were made with conductivity water. All solution mixtures shown in the tables were prepared from these parent solutions. The p_H of all solutions was measured at room temperature by a Beckman p_H -meter (type G). It has been observed that the p_H of each solution mixture (*i*) continuously goes on decreasing for some time after which the p_H becomes constant and, evidently, a few hours are required for the equilibrium to be attained. The reading for each solution was repeated in duplicate in all cases, and in many cases in triplicate, using each time a solution mixture independently prepared from the same stock solutions, or sometimes from different stock solutions, and in all cases the readings agreed within ± 0.01 p_H unit.

* This was done since $\log f_1$ and $\log f_2$ are linearly related to $\sqrt{\mu}$ and ' f_1 ' and ' f_2 ' both become equal to unity when $\sqrt{\mu} = 0$ (vide equations 8a and 8b).

TABLE I

Concentration of parent solutions.

x.	Solution mixtures in c.c.			M/10; C=0.1; p=r. Temp.=34°.		M/5; C=0.2; p=r. Temp.=32°.		M/3; C=0.333; p=r. Temp.=32°.	
	HAc.	Pb(NO ₃) ₂ .	Water.	p _H .	Increase in [H ⁺] (Y × 10 ⁴).	p _H .	Increase in [H ⁺] (Y × 10 ⁴).	p _H .	Increase in [H ⁺] (Y × 10 ⁴).
0.10	1	9	...	2.73		2.43		2.22	
	1	...	9	3.40	13.0	3.23	28.9	3.12	48.7
	...	9	1	3.80		3.62		3.40	
0.20	2	8	...	2.65		2.30		2.12	
	2	...	8	3.20	18.1	3.05	39.0	2.95	59.9
	...	8	2	4.15		3.65		3.32	
0.30	3	7	...	2.55		2.25		2.07	
	3	...	7	3.10	19.6	2.96	43.9	2.89	67.4
	...	7	3	4.15		3.88		3.32	
0.40	4	6	...	2.50		2.23		2.00	
	4	...	6	3.05	21.8	2.94	46.1	2.83	81.7
	...	6	4	4.03		3.90		3.45	
0.45	4.5	5.5	...	...		2.22		1.99	
	4.5	...	5.5	...	...	2.93	17.5	2.82	84.0
	...	5.5	4.5	...		4.00		3.50	
0.50	5	5	...	2.48		2.20		1.98	
	5	...	5	3.00	22.7	2.91	50.0	2.80	86.5
	...	5	5	4.35		4.10		3.63	
0.55	5.5	4.5	...	...		2.20		1.98	
	...	4.5	5.5	...	...	2.90	49.6	2.78	86.1
	...	5.5	...	...		4.07		3.79	
0.60	6	4	...	2.49		2.21		1.99	
	6	...	4	2.95	20.7	2.88	47.8	2.74	82.7
	...	4	6	4.32		4.16		3.81	
0.65	6.5	3.5	...	...		2.22		2.00	
	6.5	...	3.5	...	...	2.78	43.2	2.73	80.1
	...	3.5	6.5	...		4.27		3.90	
0.70	7	3	...	2.50		2.22		2.02	
	7	...	3	2.90	18.6	2.75	42.1	2.71	74.5
	...	3	7	4.45		4.44		3.97	
0.75	7.5	2.5	...	...		2.25		2.03	
	7.5	...	2.5	...	...	2.73	37.2	2.71	73.1
	...	2.5	7.5	...		4.45		4.14	
0.80	8	2	...	2.53		2.27		2.13	
	8	...	2	2.85	15.3	2.71	33.9	2.66	51.7
	...	2	8	5.10		4.57		4.30	
0.90	9	1	...	2.60		2.35		2.15	
	9	...	1	2.85	10.9	2.69	24.2	2.64	46.9
	...	1	9	5.05		4.90		4.70	

The results of the p_H measurements are tabulated in Table I. The values of 'Y' have been plotted against the corresponding values of 'x' in Fig. 1. Curves I, II and III refer to $C=0.1, 0.2$ and 0.333 respectively for both parent solutions.

Fig. 1

TABLE II

Solution mixtures in c.c. Concentration of parent solutions.

x.	Solution mixtures in c.c.		M/10; C=0.1; p=1. Temp=34°.		M/5; C=0.2; p=1. Temp=32°.		M/3; C=0.333; p=1. Temp=32°.	
	HAc	Pb (NO ₂) ₂	μ .	$K \times 10^3$.	μ .	$K \times 10^3$.	μ .	$K \times 10^3$.
0.10	1.0	9.0	0.2682	0.260	0.5364	0.085	0.8923	0.024*
0.20	2.0	8.0	0.2377	0.346	0.4752	0.119	0.7919	0.048
0.30	3.0	7.0	0.2075	0.450	0.4147	0.170	0.6912	0.080
0.40	4.0	6.0	0.1772	0.496	0.3545	0.236	0.5898	0.092
0.45	4.5	5.5	...	...	0.3244	2.266	0.5398	0.103
0.50	5.0	5.0	0.1472	0.573	0.2942	0.278	0.4895	0.125
0.55	5.5	4.5	...	...	0.2642	0.310	0.4398	0.148
0.60	6.0	4.0	0.1174	0.720	0.2344	0.378	0.3900	0.184
0.65	6.5	3.5	...	...	0.2047	0.416	0.3405	0.213
0.70	7.0	3.0	0.0876	0.840	0.1747	0.477	0.2909	0.282
0.75	7.5	2.5	...	...	0.1453	0.592	0.2415	0.329
0.80	8.0	2.0	0.0580	0.972	0.1156	0.673	0.1936	0.614
0.90	9.0	1.0	0.0287	1.103	0.0569	0.879	0.0943	0.642

N.B. The ionisation constant of acetic acid (HAc) at the temperature of the experiment (32°-40°) has been taken to be $K_1=1.75 \times 10^{-5}$ ("The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions" by Harned and Owen, Ed. II, p. 580).

* Not shown in Fig. 3, but it will fall on the same straight line.

The values of ' μ ' and ' K ' (vide equs. 7 and 1a respectively) obtained by following different stages of calculation, as shown before, are shown in Table II. The values

FIG. 2

of ' K ' obtained in Table II have been plotted against the corresponding values of the ionic strength ' μ ' in Fig. 2 and, as stated already, all the points have been found to

FIG. 3

The sign $\star$ represents the plot ϕK against $\sqrt{\mu}$ (mean) from Part III.

lie on the same smooth curve, proving definitely the dependence of the values of ' K ', calculated by the above method, on the respective ionic strength. In Fig. 3 the values of $pK = (-\log K)$ have been plotted against the corresponding values of $\sqrt{\mu}$ from Table II, and it can be seen that all the points lie on the same straight line; this when extrapolated to $\sqrt{\mu} = 0$, gives the value of pK representing the negative exponent of the true thermodynamic constant ' K '. This value is $pK = 2.48$ and hence, $K = 3.31 \times 10^{-3}$ at $32^\circ - 34^\circ$.

DISCUSSION

From the review of the work done in the past fifty years on the complexes formed between lead and acetate ions, summarised by Purkayastha and Sen Sarma (this *Journal*, *loc. cit.*), it is clear that the most stable complex formed in solution by mixing lead and acetate ions is $[\text{PbAc}]^+$; the higher acetate complexes are not formed in significant amounts when the acetate ion concentration is small. The study of lead nitrate and acetic acid mixtures by Job's method in the present work also corroborates this view. Considerable difference in opinion, however, exists as regards the value of the dissociation constant, ' K ', for the complex $[\text{PbAc}]^+$. Edmonds and Birnbaum (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2367) from a study of the solubility of lead iodate in solutions containing varying amounts of acetate ion at constant ionic strength, adjusted by adding appropriate amounts of ammonium perchlorate, concluded that $K = 9.65 \times 10^{-3}$ at 25° for $[\text{PbAc}]^+$ (mean value worked out from several values given). Though this value represents approximately thermodynamic constant, ' K ', at the particular ionic strength employed, it is not certainly the true value for ' K ' since the activity coefficients for the ions at the ionic strength employed are much less than unity and so they do not cancel out. Moreover, Purkayastha and Sen Sarma (*loc. cit.*) have pointed out that the conclusion of Edmonds and Birnbaum are based on certain arbitrary assumptions, not often justifiable.

Purkayastha and Sen Sarma (*loc. cit.*) from a study of the conductivities of solution mixtures of lead nitrate and ammonium acetate by Job's method of continued variation concluded that the dissociation constant ' K ' for $[\text{PbAc}]^+$ was 40.76×10^{-3} at 30° . This work too, is open to the following objections.

(a). Job's method cannot yield an accurate value of ' K ' for reasons already stated. However, the composition of the complex determined by this method is fairly reliable.

(b). The specific conductivity is not strictly an additive molecular property, since the specific conductivity of the mixture would be definitely lower than the sum of the specific conductivities of the individual parent solutions at the same dilutions, even if there is no reaction between the two, as the ionic strength of the mixture is greater.

(c). The value of ' K ' obtained by Job's method is not the thermodynamic one in cases where the reactants and resultants are ions.

Das, Aditya and Prasad (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 169) from an E. M. F. study of the cell,

have found out the thermodynamic dissociation constant of the ion $[\text{PbAc}]^+$ as 3.1×10^{-3} , assuming complete dissociation of stage (I) of the following scheme of dissociation of lead acetate in aqueous solution,

In a later communication Aditya and Prasad (*ibid.*, 1953, 30, 213) from a study of the E.M.F. of cells of the type,

came to the conclusion that the first stage dissociation of lead acetate was substantially incomplete, and combining the E.M.F. data of both types of cells, they calculated the thermodynamic constant ' K_1 ' and ' K_2 ' for the first and second stages of dissociation respectively shown above; the values of ' K_1 ' and ' K_2 ' were 30×10^{-3} and 3.7×10^{-3} respectively.

The value of ' K ' given by Aditya and Prasad ($K = 3.7 \times 10^{-3}$ at 30°) (*loc. cit.*), however, appears to be the most satisfactory and agrees well with the value ($K = 3.31 \times 10^{-3}$ at $32.0-34.0^\circ$) obtained in the present work by an independent method, free from practically all the objections raised in the previous cases. The only approximation made is the neglect of the formation of polyacetato plumbites. The possibility of formation of higher acetato plumbites, e.g. PbAc_n ($n = 2, 3, 4$ etc), in the system "lead nitrate - acetic acid - water" is however small, since $[\text{Ac}^-]$ in such a system is very low, the dissociation of acetic acid in water being very poor. Moreover, the presence of preponderating amounts of the complex PbAc^+ in preference to higher acetato plumbites, is amply demonstrated by the value of $m/n = 1$, obtained by the present work and by Purkayastha and Sen Sarma (*loc. cit.*) using Job's method of continued variation. Purkayastha and Sen Sarma have used ammonium acetate solution in which $[\text{Ac}^-]$ is very large, and there is a greater possibility of formation of higher acetato plumbites than in the present work, and if acetato plumbites are formed to any appreciable extent, the value of ' K ' determined by Purkayastha and Sen Sarma would be more erroneous, for then, Job's formula in the form used by the authors would not have been applicable.

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